

The effects of humidity on ester hydrolysis and oxidation in aging oil paint

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A Additional ATR-FTIR spectra of aging oil paints

A.1 Details of ATR-FTIR spectra of LOp during aging

LOp, 75 RH%, T = 70 °C

Figure S1: ATR-FTIR spectra of LOp during aging at 75 %RH and 70 °C between (a) 450–4000 cm⁻¹, (b) 450–1300 cm⁻¹, (c) 1300–2000 cm⁻¹ and (d) 2000–4000 cm⁻¹. The mean of the ATR-FTIR spectra at each unique time point is shown after baseline correction (average absorbance between 1820 cm⁻¹ and 1840 cm⁻¹) and normalization at 1456 cm⁻¹.

A.2 The carbonyl region in LOp, R50 and B50 under different humidity conditions

LOp, T = 70 °C

Figure S2: ATR-FTIR spectra of LOp (1500–1900 cm⁻¹) during aging at 70 °C at (a) 11 %RH, (b) 28 %RH, (c) 50 %RH and (d) 75 %RH. The mean of the ATR-FTIR spectra at each unique time point is shown after baseline correction (1480–1820 cm⁻¹) and normalization at 1456 cm⁻¹.

R50, T = 70 °C

Figure S3: ATR-FTIR spectra of R50 (1500–1900 cm⁻¹) during aging at 70 °C between at (a) 11 %RH, (b) 28 %RH, (c) 50 %RH and (d) 75 %RH. The mean of the ATR-FTIR spectra at each unique time point is shown after baseline correction (1480–1820 cm⁻¹) and normalization at 1456 cm⁻¹.

B50, T = 70 °C

Figure S4: ATR-FTIR spectra of B50 (1500–1900 cm⁻¹) during aging at 70 °C between at (a) 11 %RH, (b) 28 %RH, (c) 50 %RH and (d) 75 %RH. The mean of the ATR-FTIR spectra at each unique time point is shown after baseline correction (1480–1820 cm⁻¹) and normalization at 1456 cm⁻¹

B Additional dynamic vapor sorption data

B.1 Equilibrium moisture concentration of non-aged B50, W67, R50 and LOp

Changes in sample masses were converted to water concentrations in the cured binder by assuming that

1. the pigment particles do not absorb any water
2. there is no empty space in the oil paint
3. the density of the oil binder does not change significantly during curing

The volume of the binding medium was calculated by using the binder mass fraction of each paint and the density of linseed oil (0.942 g mL^{-1}).

Figure S5: Equilibrium moisture sorption isotherms of non-aged W67 (blue), LOp (yellow), B50 (black) and R50 (red), expressed as $m_{\text{water}}/V_{\text{LO}}$.

B.2 Full DVS data of R50 and W67 paints as function of aging time

R50, 75 RH%, T = 70 °C

Figure S6: Equilibrium moisture sorption isotherms of R50 during different times of aging under 70 °C and 75 %RH. The mass change is compared to its initial weight before performing the experiment.

W67, 75 RH%, T = 70 °C

Figure S7: Equilibrium moisture sorption isotherms of W67 during different times of aging under 70 °C and 75 %RH. The mass change is compared to its initial weight before performing the experiment.

C Estimating carbonyl species concentrations using ATR-FTIR spectroscopy

C.1 Calibration series

A calibration series of ATR-FTIR spectra was prepared to estimate the concentrations of esters and CAK species in aging oil paint films. As reference, we used mixtures of ethyl linoleate and octanoic acid in various ratios, as these are expected to have carbonyl group extinction coefficients similar to those in (aged) linseed oil triglycerides.

Figure S8a shows a typical ATR-FTIR spectrum in the carbonyl region of a mixture of octanoic acid and ethyl linoleate. The carbonyl bands were described exceptionally well by Lorentzian band shapes. Therefore, we chose to model the bands in these model mixtures with a set of Lorentzians, even though in polymerized and aged linseed oil, the contributions to the carbonyl region were best described by Gaussian band shapes.

Figure S8: (a) An example of an ATR-FTIR spectrum for a 80/20 volume ratio of octanoic acid and ethyl linoleate, modeled with two Lorentzian curves. (b) The calculated band areas vs. molar concentration of octanoic acid and ethyl linoleate, showing an approximately linear relationship. The spectra were baselined between 1500–1820 cm⁻¹ and normalized at 1456 cm⁻¹.

The relative concentrations of esters and carboxylic acids were determined with respect to the CH₂-groups. The calibration line is shown in Figure S8b. The normalized band areas show a linear relationship with concentration for both carboxylic acids and esters. The slopes of the lines were very similar, indicating that the extinction coefficients of acid and ester carbonyls are comparable.

To use the calibration results for concentration estimates in aging oil paints, the starting concentration of CH₂-groups in linseed oil was determined using a typical fatty acid composition of linseed oil, yielding a value of 39.4 M CH₂ for LO. The corresponding trendline equation was rewritten to determine the concentration of ester and carboxylic acids in linseed oil paints in the following way

$$C_{\text{ester}} = \frac{A_{\text{ester}} + 0.4}{0.940} \times \frac{1}{39.4} \quad (1)$$

$$C_{\text{CAK}} = \frac{A_{\text{CAK}} - 0.74}{0.973} \times \frac{1}{39.4} \quad (2)$$

in which C_{ester} and C_{CAK} are the concentrations of esters and CAKs, respectively, and A_{ester} and A_{CAK} the normalized areas under the curves ((CH₂-peak, 1456 cm⁻¹)), respectively.

C.2 Determining the concentration of CH₂ groups in linseed oil

A general composition of LO is displayed in Table 1. The concentration of triglycerides in linseed oil was determined by dividing the density of linseed oil (942 kg m⁻³) with the determined molecular weight (g mol⁻¹) of an average triglyceride in linseed oil. The average concentration of CH₂ per average triglyceride molecule and the total concentration of CH₂ in linseed oil were determined. The total concentration of CH₂ in linseed oil was determined to be 38.4 M.

Table 1: Typical composition of linseed oil [4].

Compound	n CH ₂ / n _{compound}	Mass [wt.%]	MW [g / mol ⁻¹]	n _{compound} [mol / 100 g _{LO}]	n _{compound} / n _{total} [%]	(n CH ₂ / n _{compound}) * (n _c / n _{total})
Palmitic acid	14	5.9	256.430	0.02	6.37%	0.91
Stearic acid	16	3.1	284.484	0.01	3.03%	0.39
Oleic acid	14	17	282.468	0.06	16.75%	2.62
Linoleic acid	12	16.4	280.452	0.06	16.27%	2.87
Alpha-linolenic acid	10	57.6	278.436	0.21	57.57%	4.74
Total	-	100	276.9	-	100 %	11.43
Triglyceride	-	-	830.85	-	-	38.39

C.3 Fitting procedure for the carbonyl region in ATR-FTIR spectra of oil paints

The carbonyl region was modeled using a constrained fit with six Gaussian functions. Fit optimization was carried out using the open source library SciPy and the in-built function ‘curve_fit’. We used the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm for constrained curve fitting, with the parameter limits as shown in Table 2.

As mentioned in the main text, the extent of band overlap and variations in band widths and positions over the course of aging made it impossible to explicitly model and assign all contributions to the carbonyl region. Instead, we modeled the spectral range between 1500 and 1800 cm⁻¹ with six Gaussian band shapes, assigning the contribution centered close to 1710 cm⁻¹ to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{CAK}}$ (a group containing carboxylic acids, ketones and aldehydes), the contribution at 1738 cm⁻¹ to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})_{\text{ester}}$ and the contribution at 1760 cm⁻¹ to the carbonyl vibration of lactones or other secondary oxidation products [1]. Between 1500–1650 cm⁻¹, no distinct band was identified, but we observed a broad absorption tail. This tail may be caused in part by a strong asymmetry in the shape of the carboxylic acid band in polymerized oil. However, this region can contain various non-carbonyl vibrations, like the bending mode of water, and hence was excluded from the analysis of the carbonyl region. Therefore, we chose to consider this absorption tail as background signal, and to model it using three additional Gaussian band shapes, after confirming that the positions of these additional bands remained approximately constant throughout the artificial aging period. Using fewer bands did not lead to satisfactory fits. An example of an implementation of this fitting procedure is shown in Figure S9 for LOP aged for 83 days at 75 %RH.

Table 2: Parameter limits for modeling the carbonyl region in ATR-FTIR spectra between 1500–1800 cm⁻¹ with six Gaussian band shapes.

	μ_{min} (cm ⁻¹)	μ_{max} (cm ⁻¹)	σ_{min} (cm ⁻¹)	σ_{max} (cm ⁻¹)	A_{min}	A_{max}
Band 1	1550	1600	0	100	0	4
Band 2	1625	1645	0	35	0	4
Band 3	1650	1670	0	30	0	4
Band 4	1690	1710	0	100	0	4
Band 5	1730	1750	0.3	100	0	4
Band 6	1750	1790	0	100	0	4

Figure S9: ATR-FTIR spectra of LOp (1500–1900 cm^{-1}) after aging at 75 %RH and 70 °C for 83 days. The mean of the ATR-FTIR spectra at each unique time point is shown after baseline correction (1480–1820 cm^{-1}) and normalization at 1456 cm^{-1} . Six Gaussians were fitted using the initial constraints in Table 2.

D Pigment analysis using powder X-ray diffraction

Powder X-ray Diffraction (pXRD) measurements were carried out using a Rigaku MiniFlex II diffractometer with a Ni-filtered Cu K α source ($\lambda = 1.540562 \text{ \AA}$) operated at 30 kV and 15 mA. A NaI(Tl) scintillation detector with a Be window (23 mm diameter, 80 mm length) was used for X-ray detection. A glass sample holder with a 0.2 mm deep and 8 mm diameter cavity was used. The pigments were ground and pressed into the cavity of the sample holder to create a uniform and flat surface. Excessive material was removed with a cotton swab. All measurements were carried out in the range of 5–50° (2θ). The resolution of the measurement was 0.05° with a scanning rate of 1°/min. The obtained diffractograms are depicted in Figure S10. The red iron oxide pigment was pure hematite and zinc white was pure zincite. For vine black, a mostly amorphous material was found with some main distinct phases of quartz (12.75° and 27.70°), calcite (29.55°) and dolomite (30.90°).[3, 2]

Figure S10: Powder X-ray diffractogram of the used (a) red iron oxide, (b) zinc oxide and (c) vine black pigments for preparing the paint films. The resolution was 0.05° with a scanning rate of 1°/min.

References

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